

QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF BONDED JOINTS FOR REPAIR PURPOSES WITH ADHESIVE FILMS AND LAMINATING RESINS

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SUMMARY

A comparison between the fracture toughness of bonded joints manufactured with two adhesive films and two laminating resins is presented with the objective to assess their quality for repair purposes. Experimental procedures, as the use of different standards or the effect of stiffening the adherents with metal plates are investigated and discussed.

Keywords: Bonded Joints, Adhesives, Fracture Toughness, Repair, Double Cantilever Beam

INTRODUCTION

There is a current need to establish well proven and efficient procedures to repair aircraft composite structures. Adhesion between the structure and the repair patch is a key factor for the success of the operation. The out-of-autoclave curing procedure rules out the possibility to use standard materials for primary structures or, at least, requires a careful assessment of their performance in those conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to have reliable experimental tests at the specimen scale to characterize the quality of the bonded joint and to provide the required parameters for a safe design.

Nowadays, the fracture toughness of bonded joints is determined by means of standard tests formerly developed for delamination characterization [1] (ASTM D5528-01 [2], ISO-15024 [3]). These tests are time consuming and expensive because they involve monitoring the crack length during the experiment. Therefore, aircraft industries have developed internal and simpler procedures to estimate the fracture toughness (AITM1-0053 [4]). The data reduction procedure for this test relies on the "area method" (the integral of the Load-Displacement curve as a measure of the energy involved in the crack extension).

In this communication, a comparison of the Mode I fracture toughness under static loads of two adhesive films and two laminating resins is conducted in order to assess the quality of the bonded joints for repair purposes. Besides this intrinsic comparison, this communication includes some studies on the methodologies to evaluate the quality of the bonded joint: a correlation between the ultrasonic C-scan attenuation and the fracture toughness of the joint, the analysis of the effect of stiffening the composite adherents with an aluminium plate on the G_{IC} results, and a comparison of standard test methods (AITM 1-0053 [4] and ISO 15024 [3]).

EXPERIMENTAL

Two adhesive films, A1 and A2 and two laminating resins L1 and L2 were used to manufacture bonded joints between carbon fibre reinforced pre-cured adherents, AS4 / 8552 unidirectional (UD) prepreg from Hexcel. The ply sequence for the adherents was $[0_2, \pm 45_2]_s$. The adherent panels were pre-cured in autoclave at 180°C and 7 bar. Then, the bonded joint was performed in a furnace with the assistance of a vacuum bag. The adhesive films studied (A1, A2) are normally processed in the autoclave and there was an interest to assess their mechanical performance in field repair conditions, where the use of autoclave is usually precluded. A teflon insert was placed between the adherents so that an initial pre-crack of 25 mm was obtained.

For the laminating resin L1, a thermal cycle of 24 hours at room temperature followed by 2 hours at 93°C was used. For laminating resin L2, a thermal cycle of 24 hours at room temperature followed by 1 hour at 60°C and 2.5 hours at 120°C was used. The film adhesives were cured at 120°C for 120 minutes. A reference panel of a bonded joint with a well-known adhesive film (ADR) cured under autoclave conditions was also produced. That panel was used as a reference for C-scan through transmission ultrasonic inspection (using a reflectant plate).

Three panels of each adhesive/resin joint were manufactured, named as "a", "b" and "c". The dimensions of the panel were 300 x 350 mm and 8 specimens of 250 x 25 were obtained from each one. Specimens from panel "a" of each combination (A1a, A2a, L1a, L2a) were tested according to AITM standard [4]. Specimens from panels "b" were tested according to ISO 15024 standard [3]. Finally, specimens from panels "c" were stiffened by means of an aluminium sheet (Al 2024 T3, 0.8 mm in thickness) bonded to both sides of the specimen. Specimens "c" were tested according to the ISO standard [3]. Each manufactured panel was inspected by ultrasonic through transmission C-scan using a reflectance plate. Figure 1 shows the attenuation measured in each panel. Each panel was divided in two (Left and Right) in order to fit the C-scan measuring capabilities of the system. Each plot in figure 1 contains the reference panel on the left and the two halves of the panel on the right.

Mechanical tests were performed in a 100 kN MTS Insignia testing machine equipped with a 1 kN load cell. The crack length during ISO tests was monitored with a macro lens coupled to a digital camera. Figure 2 shows the experimental setup for mechanical testing. Fractographic analysis of the samples was conducted by means of a fluorescence optical microscope LEICA DMR-XA at a 10X magnification. The use of fluorescence system enhanced the contrast between the carbon fibres and the matrix and allowed to distinguish the matrix of the adherent from the bonding agent (adhesive film or laminating resins).

Fig. 1. C-scan ultrasonic inspection of the manufactured panels. Each plot shows the reference panel on the left, and the two halves of the panel on the right. At the bottom of the figure the amplitude scale is shown. High amplitudes correspond to less attenuation, thus, better quality of the bonded joint.

RESULTS

Fig. 2. Experimental setup for Mode I testing of bonded joints

Mechanical Testing

Due to the interest in identifying materials suitable for repair purposes, the bonded joints were prepared in out-of-autoclave conditions. The adhesive films studied (A1, A2) are normally processed in the autoclave and there was an interest to assess their mechanical performance in repair conditions. On the other hand, it was desired to explore the suitability of laminating resins (L1, L2) for repair operations.

The mechanical performance of the joints was measured through fracture toughness measurements under Mode I loading.

Tests according to AITM 1-00053 standard [4] were performed. This standard corresponds essentially to a Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test. The fracture toughness is determined as the quotient between the area integral under the load-displacement curve and the crack length

increment. The crosshead speed in this standard is 10 mm/min. The aim of this test is to provide a fast and cost-effective measurement of the average fracture toughness, G_{IC} .

Figure 3 shows the results (white bars) for AITM tests. The average fracture toughness of the adhesives were 1097.91 J/m^2 for A1 and 1082.24 J/m^2 for A2. These values were almost one order of magnitude larger than those obtained with laminating resins: 120.91 J/m^2 for L1 and 131.85 J/m^2 for L2.

Another interest of this study was to analyze the differences of the results obtained with AITM and ISO standards. ISO standard is based on the same specimen and loading geometry (a DCB test). In this case, the crosshead speed is reduced (between 1 and 5 mm/min) and the data reduction procedures aim to provide initiation and propagation values of fracture toughness (not the average as in AITM). This purpose obliges the crack length to be monitored during the experiment, which complicates the test procedure (need for a movable magnifying optical device, preparation of the specimen, etc.). The data reduction methodology relies on the compliance calibration of the specimen during the test.

In order to compare both standards, this study was focused on propagation data of G_{IC} rather than on initiation values. Therefore, two measurements of G_{IC} were considered: i) the average value of propagation data following the MCC method (Modified Compliance Calibration); whenever possible they were taken at the crack lengths recommended by the standard, and ii) the result of applying the area method on the load-displacement curve (this method is not considered in the standard).

Fig. 3. Mode I fracture toughness data, G_{IC} , for adhesive films and laminating resins tested according to AITM1-00053 and ISO-15024 standards. Data reduction methods for the ISO tests were the "area" method and the average over propagation values. The plot shows the panel from which the specimens were cut.

The results are illustrated in Figure 3 (light and dark gray bars). The values obtained for the adhesive films using the area method were 1197.99 J/m^2 for A1 and 1055.20 J/m^2 for A2, whereas for the laminating resins the results were 116.88 J/m^2 for L1 and 176.37 J/m^2 for L2. The average of the MCC propagation data over the same results gave 1241.69 J/m^2 for A1 and 1047.89 J/m^2 for A2, 121.70 J/m^2 for L1 and 181.30 J/m^2 for L2.

A third set of tests were performed on stiffened specimens by means of aluminium sheets bonded to each side of the specimens (as described in the "Experimental" section). Doubler reinforcement plates for delamination resistance testing are used in cases where premature failure of one specimen arm is observed. This may occur in thin specimens or in high toughness laminates [5, 6]. However, the effect of stiffening the specimens on the fracture toughness measurement was unclear to the authors of this study. Therefore, ISO tests were performed and the results compared to those of unstiffened specimens. Regarding the data reduction method for these stiffened specimens, it was considered that only the Modified Compliance Calibration method was suitable for this case. This method does not rely on a beam theory and the only assumption is that the specimen compliance "C" depends on the crack length "a" as $C \propto a^3$. According to the ISO standard, the validity of this assumption is checked for every specimen by

performing a linear fit of $\left(\frac{BC}{N}\right)^{1/3}$ versus $a/2h$ where "B" is the specimen width, "N" the

load block correction and "h" the specimen arm thickness (including the aluminium doubler). The correlation factor of these fits for each stiffened specimen was excellent.

For the adhesive films, the area method provided 1459.65 J/m^2 for A1, 1214.27 J/m^2 for A2, 125.41 J/m^2 for L1 and 141.36 J/m^2 for L2. The averaged propagation data produced 1446.81 J/m^2 for A1, 1107.09 J/m^2 for A2, 121.23 J/m^2 for L1 and 136.72

J/m^2 for L2. Figure 4 shows the obtained results for non-stiffened and stiffened specimens.

Table 1 summarizes all the obtained results of G_{IC} for the different bonded joints and testing methods.

Fig. 4. Mode I fracture toughness for stiffened and non-stiffened specimens tested according to the ISO standard.

Table 1. Summary of results

			Adhesive films		Laminating resins	
			A1	A2	L1	L2
AITM (a)	area	Average (J/m^2)	1097.91	1082.24	120.91	131.85
	average propagation	Average (J/m^2)	1241.69	1047.89	121.70	181.30
ISO non-stiffened (b)	area	Average (J/m^2)	1197.99	1055.20	116.88	176.37
	average propagation	Average (J/m^2)	1241.69	1047.89	121.70	181.30
ISO stiffened (c)	area	Average (J/m^2)	1459.65	1214.27	125.41	141.36
	average propagation	Average (J/m^2)	1446.81	1107.09	121.23	136.72

Fractographic analysis

A transverse section of one specimen of each batch was inspected by optical microscopy after mechanical testing. The sample was prepared by cutting a slab of the specimen, then mounting it in an epoxy matrix and finally grinding and polishing (common metallographic sample preparation).

Figure 5 shows one example of the optical inspection for each bonded joint.

Fig. 5. Fractographic analysis by fluorescence optical microscopy of a cross-section of the bonded joints after testing.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Micrographs shown in figure 5 evidences that adhesive films and laminating resins produced a different failure scenario. In bonded joints of both adhesive films the failure was entirely cohesive; no de-adhesion between adherent and adhesive was observed in any of the samples inspected. In case of laminating resin L1, the micrographs suggest that wetting of the adherents by the resin was incomplete with areas of adhesive failure. The areas where the resin stuck to the adherent exhibit cohesive failure. In case of laminating resin L2, the resin pulled out part of the matrix of the upper adherent (the upper side in the photograph of figure 5), indicating that the strength of the interface was not particularly weak but the inability of the resin for plastic deformation leading to a low fracture toughness of the bonded joint.

Whichever failure micromechanism, it was clearly evidenced in this study that the adhesive films A1 and A2 processed in out-of-autoclave conditions, exhibited a much larger fracture toughness than laminating resins. Both adhesive films adhered properly to the adherents and the level of porosity and defects was similar to that of the adhesive films cured in autoclave conditions.

Concerning the methodological investigation, the following conclusions and remarks can be issued from this study:

- In three (A1, A2, L1) of the four bonding agents tested, the averaged values of fracture toughness calculated by means of the area method do not depend on the crosshead speed (5 or 10 mm/min). Only in laminating resin L2, there is a relative increase of 34% in the G_{IC} average in the specimens tested at 5 mm/min (L2b) with respect to the specimens tested at 10 mm/min (L2a). However, the fact that the fracture toughness calculated with stiffened specimens (L2c) coincides with the fracture toughness of L2a and the abnormal C-scan attenuation of panel L2b (figure 1), suggest that this difference might be attributed to a difference in the panel rather than a consequence of the crosshead speed.
- In tests performed under ISO standard, and for all bonded joints analyzed in this study, the averaged values of fracture toughness measured by means of the area method or by averaging propagation data are equivalent.
- Adding aluminium doublers to each side of the specimens to stiffen them does not impede the use of the data reduction method of the ISO standard based on the Modified Compliance Calibration. The specimen compliance was demonstrated to correlate well with the third power of the crack length.
- The fact of stiffening the specimens has a different effect over the measured fracture toughness for the different bonded joints. In the case of adhesive films, average G_{IC} seems to increase slightly (20% for A1 and 13% for A2) over the results obtained with non-stiffened specimens as well as the coefficient of variation. Average values of fracture toughness of laminating resins did not vary when stiffening the specimens (if results for L2b are considered to be anomalous as explained above) and there is not a clear trend on the coefficient of variation.

In summary, for the bonded joints tested in this study, and provided that the interest is on averaged values of fracture toughness rather than on initiation values, the area method (either applied to AITM or ISO test data) provided consistent results with

moderate dispersion (coefficient of variation). Stiffening the specimens with aluminium doublers does not introduce clear advantages over non-stiffened specimens.

The adhesive films tested (A1 and A2) are more suitable for repair operations than the laminating resins studied (L1 and L2) in terms of mechanical performance.

The investigation on these adhesive films and laminating resins is on course with tests on samples in hot/wet conditions, fatigue tests and by exploring the fracture toughness of the bond when the patch is co-cured with the bonding agent to a pre-cured adherent.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has been partially funded by AIRBUS España contract A8210153G and by the Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia from the Spanish Government under contract MAT2006-14159-C02-01.

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